

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, titled “D6.1 Software Requirements Specification”, is a comprehensive description of the intended purpose and environment for the EcoBulk Project’s software systems under development, describing how the systems interacts with human users and other software programs or hardware systems.

This deliverable begins with an overview of the software description and system architecture followed by a complete description of the desired behavior of the system, the specifications, the classification of the different requirements and functions and their integration.

In order to specify the software requirements and carry out development, all information related to functions and specifications must be included in this document with as much accuracy and clarity as possible. This specification is intended to serve two purposes: to describe in detail the software’s requirements and specifications in order to serve as a guide during the implementation stage, and to provide a reference to aid during the exploitation and maintenance stage.

The deliverable is based on IEEE 830 standard guidelines for specifying requirements and specifications for software development. Nevertheless, the standard requirements have been adapted to the particularities of this system.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	7
1.1	Purpose.....	7
1.2	Intended audience.....	7
1.3	Definitions	8
1.4	System overview.....	11
2	Overall description.....	12
2.1	Product perspective	12
2.2	Design constraints	16
2.3	Product actors	16
2.4	User profiles	18
2.5	Product functions.....	32
2.6	Assumptions and dependencies	38
3	Technical specifications	40
3.1	Architecture implementation	40
4	Conclusions.....	44
A	Technical Annex	

FIGURES

Figure 1.1 Work packages interdependencies.	11
Figure 2.1 Overview of the EcoBulk's software systems.	13
Figure 2.2 High-Level content of EcoBulk database and Project's Data Providers.	35
Figure 2.3 Overview of the functions of the DSS.	37
Figure 3.1 Service-oriented system architecture.	41

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

API	Application Programming Interface
DSS	Decision Support System
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
PC	Project Coordinator
QAS	Quality Assurance System
QMS	Quality Management System
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this document is to gather, analyze and present an in-depth insight of the software systems developed in the EcoBulk project by defining the problem statement in detail. Nevertheless, it also focuses on the features and functionalities required by end-users and stakeholders and their needs while defining high-level product features.

The detailed software requirements specification of the EcoBulk's software systems are provided in this document.

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of the document is to describe the specifications, integration, and classification of the different requirements and functions of the final EcoBulk's software systems in order to accurately specify the software requirements in order to carry out its correct development in an efficient and streamlined manner.

1.2 Intended audience

The intended audience for this document includes the development teams, exploitation stakeholders and operations and maintenance teams of the EcoBulk project.

The document will be used by the consortium team as the specification from which to implement the working software systems. It will also be used during the exploitation stage of the project's software in order to promote and present its different functionalities, requirements and dependencies.

Application implementers must read this document as it provides the functional specifications of the application and it should be used as a guide during the development process.

Operations teams and IT technicians should use this document as a reference for the supporting of the application's deployment and management, and for meeting the required dependencies and providing the necessary hardware and software interfaces.

Furthermore, this document will be used as a deliverable within the framework of the EcoBulk project.

1.3 Definitions

This section defines concepts of the circular supply chain framework needed for the understanding of the document.

Concept	Definition
Circular economy	A circular economy entails decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resource and designing waste and pollution out of the system. It aims to keep products and materials in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate products and materials at the end of each service life. A circular economy should build economic and social capital and regenerate natural systems.
Disposal	Any operation which is not recovery – even where the operation has a secondary consequence or leads to the reclamation of substances or of energy. This includes disposal by incineration where the incineration plant does not meet the EUs R1 energy recovery status.
Prevention	Measures taken before a substance, material or product has become waste that reduce the quantity of waste, the adverse impacts of the generated waste on environment and human health and the content of harmful substances in materials and products.
Recovery	Any operation, the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials that would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function in the plant or wider economy. This includes incineration facilities where the plant meets the EUs Recovery plant (R1) energy recovery status.
Recycling	Any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material

	but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations.
Refurbish	Return a product, component or material back to a better usable state by fixing minor issues or completing it as by renovating, re-equipping or restoring.
Remanufacturing	Return a used product to at least its original performance with a warranty that is equivalent to or better than that of the newly manufactured product.
Repair	Return a faulty or broken product, component or material back to a usable state. A repair may use remanufactured or refurbished parts.
Reuse	Any operation by which products or components that are not waste are used again for the same purpose for which they were conceived.
Waste	Any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard.
Product history	Chronologically ordered collection of events that affected a part or product, e.g. reparation instances.
End-user	Person or group of people who ultimately use or are intended to use a product.
Stakeholder	Member involved with and organization who has responsibilities towards it and interest in its success and without whose support the organization would cease to exist.
Designer	Agent that plans the look and specifies the structural properties of an object, component or product.
Manufacturer	Member or company that produces goods in large numbers (material, pieces and final products). These goods can be made from virgin and recovered raw materials.

Dismantler	Member or company that take a product apart obtaining reusable pieces or materials.
Logistics	Management of the flow of materials, pieces and products between a point of origin and a point of destination, which can be the point of consumption or the next stage in the product development.
Reverse logistics	Management of the flow of goods from the collection points for the purpose of capturing value by remanufacture, refurbish, recycle, repair, reuse or proper disposal.
Action	Process applied to a final product that is returned to a collection point in order to capture value. An action can involve a process for remanufacturing, refurbishing, recycling, repairing, reusing or the proper disposal of the product's components.

1.4 System overview

The software systems implemented in the framework of the EcoBulk project is meant to support the data storage and retrieval needs during the development of the whole project as well as the implementation of specific services with the aim demonstration solutions with the aim of supporting and promoting a more circular economy.

The following figure illustrates the high-level interdependencies between the different work packages of the project, where it can be observed a first approach of the several data flows between them. As it can be seen, the Ecobulk's software systems aim to be not only the database that stores information (such as product designs, material cards, etc.), but also a group of services capable of enabling the interaction between the actors of the circular economy and analyzing/processing the retrieved data in order to give assessment to the user of the platform by means of quality certification, support on EoL decisions.

Figure 1.1 Work packages interdependencies.

2 OVERALL DESCRIPTION

This chapter aims to provide a complete description of the system's features and design constraints for implementing the application from the point of view of an applications architect and developer.

2.1 Product perspective

The Ecobulk's software systems are envisioned as a platform which provides the circular economy actors with enhanced features and functions to promote increased circularity of the produced goods.

As aforementioned, the main objectives of a system like that is to provide a common information repository to all the actors working on a circular economy, focusing in the continuous feedback between them and enabling some intelligent services or modules which permit users to optimize their processes and therefore be more cost-effective.

The software systems can be divided into different main modules or services which are depicted in the following figure. The service inputs are inside grey and green boxes and the results of the service are those inside the blue boxes.

Figure 2.1 Overview of the EcoBulk's software systems.

The following sections present a brief description of the above modules.

2.1.1 Tracking, Labelling and Reverse logistics

The tracking system is the one that enables the traceability of the eco-designed products. It provides a unique identifier for each product that links it to information like its origin, supply chain, material composition, technical and safety datasheets or applicable quality standards among others. All this information, stored in the database, allows the user to accurately know all the details about the product he acquired and provides the required input to the other software systems.

It also handles the identification of strategies and technologies for transport and logistics optimization: this includes selection of adequate means of transport, payload capacity optimization, route planning and monitoring, traceability, demand planning and forecasting, location of collection points, warehouse positioning and management, safeguard product quality and safety.

Finally, it implements the evaluation of transport and logistic strategies and technologies: to support decision making and identify the best practices and strategies for the optimization of transport and logistics activities that take place along the collection and reverse logistics supply chains of different types of products.

2.1.2 End User and Stakeholder Platform

The Ecobulk's end-user and stakeholder platform are indented to serve two the different actor identified in the project. The **end-user platform** will implement strategies related to reusing, repairing, refurbishing, recycling and disposing to encourage the end-user of goods, particularly furniture and building components, to engage with the circular economy principles. The **stakeholder platform** would allow the different actors of the value chain (e.g., designers, manufacturers, distributors, dismantlers, etc) to share information (e.g., material properties, use patterns, etc) and services through a unified web frontend.

2.1.3 Database Management System

The database is the main core of the Ecobulk's software systems since it stores the data collected through the product life. This data has to be accessible to the stakeholders inside the project and to the other EcoBulk's software services or applications to enable the traceability of the data, the decision making and facilitate the development of a

circular supply chain. The functional and operational requirements of a Database system are related to the volume of data stored, the voracity and velocity of data exchange, the heterogenous nature of data stored (from time series to relational data or even media) and the performance required by the downstream systems. To achieve this, the 'off-the-shelf' GRANTA MI software is used as the core of this database system. There will be a double access to the database, through programmatic API and through GUI frontend as some Granta solutions (eg. MI:BOM Analyzer and MI:Explore) will be used for data entry, data visualisation and comparison, data export and reports generation.

2.1.4 Decision Support System

The Decision Support System (DSS) is a module that enhances the cost-effectiveness of a product designed for circularity by means of providing a fast and reliable tool to evaluate the product value and its potential for recovery or remanufacture processes in order to make a proposal of the most suitable solution. It is based on using the data contained in the database regarding the product and processes specifications, quality assessment, cycle time, etc. to then evaluate the cost (both economic and environmental) and predict the optimum solution for each product or component.

2.1.5 Quality Assurance System

The scale of the project requires quality evaluation processes taking place at several stages of the production and recovery of eco-designed products. For this reason, it is important to develop a tool to ensure the uniformity between lots, reduce the number of quality control checks and reduce errors. The quality assurance system is a unit intended to provide informational support to the production chain and guarantee the correct selection of parameters, values, tests, standards and regulations for Quality Control using AI techniques to organize and process the "knowledge base".

The Quality Assurance System (QAS) acts will effectively reduce the quality variance between lots, assuring the conformity between supply chain steps. It will also avoid the problem of Nonconforming products between clients and suppliers. The QAS will be implemented using an Expert System approach together with a Cased Based Reasoning knowledge base including historical production data, rules automatically extracted from

the data, user defined rules defining tests, thresholds, official standards compliance requirements and regulations.

2.2 Design constraints

This section describes the design constraints that have been considered in order to ensure the proper operation of the software systems.

2.2.1 Operation constraints

The software systems shall be designed to be operated and accessed through a web frontend with suitable compatibility with up to date web browser in order to ensure accessibility and facilitate its availability.

Furthermore, the software shall be designed in a manner that ensures security of the data in terms of privacy of the managed information and integrity of the data.

2.2.2 Architecture constraints

The design of the software system's architecture shall follow a service oriented architecture where multiple software services collaborate in order to provide functionalities.

This provides several advantages, including that: each software service can be developed using the specific software frameworks, libraries and programming languages that are most suitable for that particular service, each service can be developed and managed by an independent team facilitating rapid implementation, each service may include their own specific data-stores for managing service-specific data, and each service may be deployed independently of the others, thus encouraging a rapid development iteration cycle.

2.3 Product actors

This section reviews the different actors, i.e. end-user and stakeholders, that interact in a circular economy model from the point of view of their role.

A company may perform different roles, but separating them shall facilitate the identification of requirements.

Furthermore, circular chain actors are split into two different groups, those that match end-users of the public-facing platform and those that are internal and refer to the stakeholders of the circular chain platform.

2.3.1 Circular-chain platform users

This category of actors within the software platform refer to the users of the manufactured products.

These users have access to the public-facing functionalities of the EcoBulk circular economy platform, but not to the Stakeholder Platform functionalities.

2.3.2 Circular-chain platform stakeholders

The following roles refer to actors and stakeholders of the EcoBulk circular economy platform.

- 1) Designers, FEA engineers.
- 2) Material experts (research or test centers, QA).
- 3) Manufacturers.
 - a) Components / pieces manufacturers.
 - b) Assembly / final product manufacturers.
- 4) Logistics.
 - a) Transport, warehouse.
 - b) Outlets.
- 5) Collection.
 - a) Collection and routing centers.
 - b) Reverse logistics.
- 6) Re-manufacturers.
 - a) Product repair.
 - b) Product refurbishing.
- 7) Waste handlers.

- a) Dismantlers, material recovery, recovered material producers.
- b) Waste disposal (circular leakage).

These actors identify what are the roles developed by companies in the scope of a circular economy chain. However, this does not mean that companies develop a single role, in practice a given company may perform a number of roles within this list.

2.4 User profiles

This section defines the user profiles for interacting with the EcoBulk’s software systems by identifying user stories for each actor or stakeholder participating in a circular economy model.

User stories take a predefined format, specifically “As an [actor] I want to [action] so that [reason]”. By using this format, the user stories that define the needs of actors within the circular economy framework, i.e. the end-users and stakeholders, were identified.

2.4.1 Product end-users

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of end-users of the products of the circular framework.

The following user stories are prefaced with “As a product end-user...”:

1. Buy a Product

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Buy a new product		
1.1.1	Know if the products comply with the necessary quality requirements / regulations (general and specific)	I can make a better decision about what product I should acquire.	
1.1.2	Be informed on the end-of life options of the products	I can take into account circularity factors when I acquire a product.	Second life programs offered by the manufacturers

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.2	Buy a second hand product		
1.2.1	Know the options to acquire a product from the circular economy supply chain	I can acquire a second hand or remanufactured product.	

2. Maintenance of a Product

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Have access to product manuals	I can maintain and repair the product myself.	
2.2	Have documentation regarding the product's use, environmental conditions and repairs	I can estimate the residual value of the product and perform preventive maintenance.	
2.3	Have information about spares & upgrades	I know what I can do with my product if it is damaged or if I want to adjust it.	

3. Repair or Remanufacture a Product

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.1	Know about collection points	I can take a product there when I want to repair it, sell it or discard it.	

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.2	Know the options to repair or remanufacture a given product	I can extend the life cycle of the product by using it longer.	

4. Dispose a Product

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
4.1	Know about collection points	I can take a product there when I want to repair it, sell it or discard it.	
4.2	Have access to disassembly instructions	I can safely & securely de-assemble the product, for transport and reselling.	

2.4.2 Designers, FEA engineers

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of designers and FEA engineers.

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a designer or engineer...":

1. Material Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Material properties		
1.1.1	Have access to available materials and their properties	I can ensure the design accomplishes the expected product's properties and cost.	Costs, usage constraints, environmental impact.

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1.2	Ensure I am using Material Cards updated and approved by Material Experts	I can perform high quality simulations.	The material cards must include both technical and safety data sheet.
1.1.3	Have information about failure modes of similar existing products	I can anticipate them in the design to prevent failures.	
1.2	Material availability		
1.2.1	Know information such as the dimensions, structural quality, etc. of the end of use components that I'm planning to reuse	I can sort them and select those that are suitable for the new product	The availability of this information determines what is the residual value of the product
1.2.2	Have access to the quantities of the available materials	I can make sure there is sufficient quantity available for production.	When choosing a recycled material, it is important that there is enough for production.

2. Quality Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Know if the product / materials comply with the necessary quality requirements / regulations (in general) and specifically for	<p>The product designed can be CE marked.</p> <p>The product is designed with the level of quality necessary within cost constraints.</p>	Regulations like: Directive 2000/53/EC, REACH 1907/2006/EC.

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
	the product / component being designed		

3. Feedback from other circular chain actors

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.1	Receive feedback about product acceptance from manufacturers, users and dismantlers	I may improve future designs for better circularity.	Suitability, issues, defects.
3.2	Have access to wear and degradation feedback from the products	I can adjust the design and material selection to prevent these type of damage	Surface degradation, wearing, UV resistance.

4. Business Models

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
4.1	Have access to information about the available recovery procedures	The design can enable necessary interventions (e.g. sharing, disassembly) by means of fastener selection, chemical composition, etc.	
4.2	Know about the intended business models of the product to be designed	The design can enable the necessary interventions.	For example, to allow sharing, disassembly, etc.

2.4.3 *Material experts*

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of material experts (research or test centers, QA).

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a materials expert...":

1. Material Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Be able to query materials information from the database	I can extract material property parameters.	
1.2	Be able to modify parameters and import data into the database	Create or update the properties of materials according to my expertise or tests performed.	

2. Quality Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Be able to consult the quality information from the QAS	I can confirm material quality testing rules, standards and regulations.	

2.4.4 *Manufacturers*

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of manufacturers in the circular supply chain, separating by component manufacturers and assemblers or final product manufacturers.

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a component manufacturer...":

1. Material Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Have access to available materials, their properties and performance, quality standards, restrictions and legislation, market acceptance	I can apply the suitable manufacturing methodology.	Technical Data Sheets Environmental Processing Guides Necessary equipment Related costs End-user material acceptance
1.2	Have access to a list of suppliers for the material	I can evaluate the supply chain stability and the business risks	

2. Quality Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Know if the pieces / components / materials comply with the necessary quality requirements / regulations (in general) and specifically for the product / component being manufactured	I can provide high quality pieces/components to assemblers, and can exclude incompliant cases.	Mechanical properties Appearance Exposure to light Exposure to chemical environment Exposure to heat Reaction to impact Surface coating

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
			Exposure to ambient air Resistance to combustion Resistance to wear

3. Feedback from other circular chain actors

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.1	Receive feedback from the assembler	I can adjust the component's properties and improve the manufacturing process.	Quality review

The following user stories are prefaced with "As an assembler or final product manufacturer...":

1. Product Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Have access to the properties of pieces and components	I can adjust the manufacturing / assembling process to improve it.	Assembly methods Necessary equipment to assemble the components (investment)
1.2	Have access to the history of a given piece or component	I can appropriately label the final product to improve user acceptance	

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
		(carbon footprint, eco-performance).	

2. Quality Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Be sure of the continued quality of the material or part	I do not face failures in the future.	

3. Feedback from other circular chain actors

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.1	Receive feedback from dismantlers and end-users	I can improve the manufacturing process to facilitate the product circularity.	Issues, ease of dismantling, times.

2.4.5 Logistics

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of logistics needs, meaning warehousing, distribution and outlets (i.e. sellers of recycled or remanufactured goods).

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a remanufactured goods logistics operator...":

1. Product Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Have access to the history and properties of a product	I can identify and classify the product.	Damage history, repair actions, supply chain data.

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
		<p>I can reduce the perceived risk for the seller, buyer and user</p> <p>I can assess the structural capacity of the product (using its repair history)</p>	Repairs may not be visible from outside
1.2	Have access to information about the origin of the product	I can use it as a selling point	Use of conflict-free materials
1.3	Know the storage conditions and toxicity	I can prevent damage due to bad storage conditions and contamination from other products	
1.4	Have access of a list of suppliers for a specific product	I can evaluate the stability and risks of the supply chain	

2. Quality Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Be able to know the product quality and have an estimation of its end of life	I can ensure that the products I sell are free of risks	

2.4.6 Collection

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of collection operators, including collection and routing centres, and reverse logistics.

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a collection and routing centre...":

1. Product Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Have access to product and material properties information	I know the recycling value if the product recovery is unfeasible	

2. End-of-Life option selection

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Be able to isolate the fault	I can do a pre-selection of product or part qualities	According to categorical quality levels: A, B, C...
2.2	Have access to the cost associated with each action (recycling, remanufacturing, and disposal)	I can decide what actions should be taken within the circular framework.	What costs? E.g.: economical, times, supply chain info.
2.3	Have a selection criteria and instructions	I can sort parts to send them to the right company	

3. Legislative and Regulatory Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.1	Have access to the legislation related to the product	I know how to handle certain material and products	

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a reverse logistics operator...":

1. Product Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Have information regarding what products to process	I can optimize the route.	Source location, destination, weight.
1.2	Know the storage conditions and toxicity	I can prevent damage due to bad storage conditions and contamination from other products	

2.4.7 Re-manufacturers

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of re-manufacturers of products within the circular supply chain, considering services such as repair, refurbishing or complete re-manufacturing.

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a product or component re-manufacturer...":

1. Product Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Being a repair service, know the history of a product or component.	I can adjust the repair process.	

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.2	Being a refurbisher, know the history of a product or component	I can adjust the refurbishing process.	
1.3	Being a remanufacturer, know the history of a product or component	I can adjust the remanufacturing process	

2. Quality Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Being a remanufacturer, know that the product/components I have been supplied with comply with the necessary quality requirements / regulations (in general) and specifically for the product / component being re-manufactured	I can ensure the high quality of the remanufactured product and can be CE marked. Also, if the product to be remanufactured will be compliant with standards requirements (EU, ISO, ...).	E.g. ELV requires removal of tires before shredding of cars.

3. Diagnosis and Identification

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.1	Have instructions regarding fault isolation, baseline measurements & testing procedures	I can evaluate residual value quickly and cost-effectively.	E.g.: the fault of a returned product has to be found <10s to be cost effective

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
3.2	Have diagnostic tools and identification systems	Disassembly, cleaning and fault isolation are time-efficient to make the component recovery economically worthwhile.	

2.4.8 Waste handlers

This section defines the user stories from the point of view of waste handlers, meaning resource recovery or disposal centres.

The following user stories are prefaced with "As a resource recovery or disposal centre...":

1. Product Information

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Being a resource recovery center, know the material chemical composition	I can ensure that the recovery process is safe for my equipment and installations	
1.2	Being a dismantler, know the history and properties of a product.	I can adjust the dismantling and material recovery actions.	
1.3	Being a waste disposal center, know the properties of a component or product	I can appropriately dispose of each material according to requirements and regulations.	What properties? E.g.: costs, regulations, H&S info.
1.4	Being a resource recovery center, have instructions for disassembly and reassembly of the product	I know how to perform the different operations and which tools are needed	

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.5	Being a resource recovery center, have access to the next production needs	I can efficiently schedule the recovery of the materials I have in my warehouse	

2. Quality Requirements

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
2.1	Being a resource recovery center, know the required quality for the recovered materials	I can adjust the recovery process to provide the desired material quality	
2.2	Know employee and environmental considerations	I can ensure that I am working under safe conditions	

2.5 Product functions

This chapter describes the functions of the product splitting them into logical groupings, linking each function to the defined user profiles.

2.5.1 Tracking, Labelling and Reverse logistics

The **labelling system** would be the market option which adapts better with the eco-innovative supply chain developed in WP5. This label will contain a unique identification number to distinguish any given object from the others, a further study to analyse the best option for the project will be developed in D6.2 Sustainable procurement, retail and product tracking and labelling system.

The **tracking system** would be implemented as a service to feed other applications and services of the stakeholder/end-user platform with logistics and transport information. Some of the functionalities will be:

- Read identification code from label.
- Check logistics and transports historical data of any given product.
- Reverse logistics recommendations.

2.5.2 End User and Stakeholder Platform

The **end-user platform** would be implemented as a web or mobile application that encourages the circularity of resources, particularly furniture and building components. It revolves around the interaction of two perspectives, one that requests for products and services within the circularity purpose and another perspective that supplies those products or services.

In particular, the platform end-user platform would allow the user to obtain or give away products following some of the strategies of the circular economy (e.g., second hand products repair products, reuse products, refurbish products or recycle products). Some of the functions that would be performed by the platform are:

Get/buy a product C2C. The user that wants to buy or get a product should be able to see the adds that other users have posted. In order to do so, there must be a search bar in which the user specifies the item she/he is looking for. A list of coincidences is then showed. The list is also available to be seen on a map that geolocates the adds that match the search query. Additionally, there is a browsing option for the user to see all the ads near a specific location.

Give away/sell a product C2C. The user that wants to sell or give away a product would be presented a form to provide the basic information of the item to sell or give away. Additional ways of obtaining that information would be allowed depending on the technology available (e.g., RFID tags, QR codes, product passport) This information will be shown as an ad and depicted on the map. It would be desirable to have an option for a user to set a "garage sell" in which multiple objects are offered in a bulk.

Get/buy a product C2B. The user has to be able to able to browse the catalogues of second-hand business. This functionality would access information of products

offered by other end-user (e.g., persons, second hand shops, remanufacturers among others). It has to consider filters to facilitate the search.

The information of this functionality would be displayed to the user as described for case Get/buy a product C2C. Moreover, the user should be able to filters the ads depending on whether the source is a person or a company.

Give away/sell a product C2B. This functionality would allow the user to sell items or take back them to companies that are interested in them. To do so, a search engine will look for companies that are interested in a specific type product. Results are shown both in a list and geolocated in a map.

A company buy - retake service (B2C). Companies would be able to post programs to buy and retake products in which they are interested. These programs are going to be showed to the user that want to sell or dispose a product.

Repairing and remanufacturing services (B2C). Companies would be able to post programs to repair and remanufacturing products in which they are interested. These programs are going to be showed to the user that want to sell or dispose a product.

Collection service for energy recovery o final dispose (B2C). This functionality would provide user with information of collection services for products when options for other loops are not available. In the end, the goal is to divert products from landfills by considering waste to energy or other strategies.

The **stakeholder platform** would integrate the different user profiles involved within the ECOBULK project allowing them the access to information generated through the different tools. For instance, it would connect designers and manufacturers through the information of materials and products acceptance rates. This platform would basically expose and allow the access to the services of the different stakeholders.

2.5.3 Database Management System

The **EcoBulk Database** will contain all the relevant data to be used by the stakeholder platform and the end-user platform. In the context of the Project/Stakeholder Platform,

we define here (image below) a number of “Data Providers”, users contributing to the database population.

Figure 2.2 High-Level content of EcoBulk database and Project’s Data Providers.

In particular the following data will be stored (with indicated the corresponding Database Table and Data Providers in the context of the EcoBulk project):

2.5.4 Decision Support System

The decision support System main function is to provide a fast and reliable way (to be cost-effective) to decide which are the best actions to perform when a product reach the collection point. In order to define this function, it has been divided in the following sub-functions:

1. In a collection point, the system shall support the user in the process of identifying and isolating the failure in a given product. For example, by indication from the user or selection from a list.
2. In a collection point, the system shall be able to define the possible actions for a product that re-enters the circular supply-chain after usage (remanufacture, refurbish, recycle, reuse and disposal), according to the product business model and the available information about the identified failure.
3. In a collection point, the system shall be able to obtain the environmental, economic and social costs associated to each of the possible actions. This costs information is gathered from the database and includes the logistics, processes and equipment needed among others.
4. In a collection point, the system shall be able to calculate the cost for each of the defined actions, taking into account a set of configurable optimization criteria. These optimization criteria can be introduced by the user or be specific for the product evaluated. In the latter case, the parameters have to be introduced to the database by the manufacturer when creating the product card.
5. In a collection point, the system shall provide the optimization results to support the decision making process. The results can be shown as a list of the previously defined actions ordered from the most to the least suitable.

These five functions are depicted in the figure below. As it can be seen, the DSS functions are placed in a sequential manner. Therefore, to be able to perform one of them, the previous functions must have been successfully completed.

The flowchart in the following figure shows that data retrieval is taking place only when the actions processes costs are needed. However, other functions may need information

from the database to identify the fault or to consult what are the possible actions defined by the manufacturers. This topic is further explained in the section 3.1.4.

Figure 2.3 Overview of the functions of the DSS.

2.5.5 Quality Assurance System

The main function of the Quality Assurance System will be to guarantee the overall quality of the material processing from beginning to end for the different sectors and actors who will use the system.

Specifically, on a user profile basis, the following functionality will be applicable:

A **product end-user** will be able to know if the products comply with the necessary quality requirements / regulations (general and specific).

A **designer** can establish if the product/materials comply with the necessary quality requirements/regulations (in general) and specifically for the product/component being designed.

A **materials expert** will be able to consult the QAS to establish material specific and generic information about quality standards.

A **manufacturer** can establish that the pieces/components/materials comply with the necessary quality requirements/regulations (in general) and specifically for the product/component being manufactured.

A **logistics operator** will be able to know the product quality and have an idea of its end of life.

A **collection operator** will be able to know the legislation for a given process / material in order to handle it correctly.

A **remanufacturer** will be able to know that the product/components which have been supplied, comply with the necessary quality requirements/regulations (in general) and specifically for the product/component being re-manufactured.

A **waste handler** will be able to know the required quality for the recovered materials.

2.6 Assumptions and dependencies

This section defines the assumptions that the software design establishes and the dependencies that are assumed to be present for the correct operation of the software systems.

2.6.1 User-side assumptions and dependencies

This subsection declares assumptions and dependencies to consider from the point of view of the user of the software systems.

In terms of general users, it is assumed that the user of the software system shall have access to a computer with access to the internet in order to interact with the software system.

In terms of end-users accessing the public-facing functionalities of the software systems, the design shall assume that the user does not know how to operate with the platform, therefore the software system shall include the necessary help features to support an inexperienced user.

In terms of users pertaining to stakeholders of the platform it is assumed that they have sufficient knowledge for interacting with the most advanced features of the stakeholder platform, or that a training program shall be made available to support them.

2.6.2 Platform-side assumptions and dependencies

This subsection declares assumptions and dependencies to consider from the point of view of the platform software, specifically regarding the availability of data for ensuring the correct operation of the software.

In terms of dependencies, some functionalities require certain data to be introduced and stored in the platform's database in order to perform certain actions. It is assumed that prior to the operation of these functionalities, the required data dependencies, specified

and required by each functionality during operation, shall be met to allow proper operation.

3 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

This chapter describes the technical specifications of the system, dividing them into implementation constraints, architecture implementation, execution environment, processes view, domain model structure diagram and its relational database schema.

3.1 Architecture implementation

Given the complexity of the software system to be implemented during the EcoBulk project, a service-based system architecture shall be adopted where the system's components are split into independent services that expose and communicate through standard APIs.

This architecture type provides several advantages over traditional monolithic approaches during the development and exploitation of the software:

- Independent teams develop and manage their own systems using the languages and tools they are most comfortable and have more experience working with.
- Code bases can be separated, contributing to rapid iterative development due to smaller, more focused implementation workflows.
- Each service exposes an API for interacting with it in a standardized manner, through HTTP endpoints.
- Each service may choose its own persistence system to store its specific data, such as decision weights or other parameters in the case of the DSS, or trends and other analytics in the case of the QAS.

The following diagram presents the high-level service-based architecture, where each node represents an executable process running independently of the others, and arrows represent the communication flow from one service to another (i.e. arrows are calls to another service's API).

Figure 3.1 Service-oriented system architecture.

The following is a brief description of the purpose and function of each of the services considered in the EcoBulk software system.

- **End-User Platform:** frontend of the user platform implemented as a web/mobile application that allows to access functionalities of the EcoBulk software system.
- **Stakeholder Platform:** frontend of the stakeholder platform implemented as a collection of tools for accessing functionalities of the EcoBulk software system, including the Granta MI tool suite and a web frontend application.
- **Security:** service that shall handle security related concerns such as authentication, authorization and managing of sessions.

- **Database:** the database service consists in the Granta Database management system which includes support for:
 - **Designs:** service that shall facilitate storage and retrieval of designs in a structured manner.
 - The database structure will aim to store all data related to Designs and aim to ensure that users create, import and find them easily. The database structure will be created from partners input in order to fit the data input and partners/customers/end-users expectations and workflow.
 - **Materials and Test Data:** service that shall facilitate storage and retrieval of materials in a structured manner.
 - The database structure will aim to store all data related to Materials and Test Data and aim to ensure that users create, import and find them easily. The database structure will be created from partners input in order to fit the data input and partners/customers/end-users allowing to create, import and find them easily, matching their expectations and workflow.
 - **Processes:** service that shall facilitate storage and retrieval of processes in a structured manner.
 - The database structure will aim to store all data related to processes and workflows.
- **Tracking, Labelling and Reverse Logistics:** the service is composed by a tracking and labelling system and a by a reverse logistics evaluation and recommendation tool:
 - **Tracking and Labelling:** the service that shall handle the issuing and management of labelling and tracking identifiers so that they can be queried by other services.
 - **Reverse Logistics module:** the service shall carry out the evaluation of transport and logistic strategies and technologies to support decision

making and identify the best practices and strategies for the optimization of transport and logistics activities that take place along the collection and reverse logistics.

- **Decision Support System:** the service shall consider economic, environmental and social aspects for making decisions regarding the optimal actions to take at the post-usage collection point in order to increase the circularity of the supply chain. Its functionality depends on other services, such as the data repository services, the tracking and labelling, transport logistics for retrieval of transport costs and the quality assurance system.
- **Quality Assurance System:** the service shall provide the Protocols, Actuation Procedures and Manufacturing Good Practices to keep updated all involved stakeholders. The QAS shall include a quality framework for consideration and balancing of competing requirements across the life-cycle to be implemented at the design stage.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This document presents an approach to the identification of the roles and profiles of the participants in a circular supply-chain economy framework.

The document includes the definition of the user roles, an in-depth study of the needs and requirements of the participants from the point of view of user stories, and the subsequent definition of product functions to solve the identified requirements.

Specific details and implementation approach are presented in a technical annex that develops the functional requirements and use cases of the software system.